

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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IMPROVING THE CRITERIA FOR SELECTING TRADITIONAL OR MODERN TECHNOLOGY AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT BASED ON THE CLINICAL CONDITION OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLETE EDENTULISM**Olimov S.Sh., Rabiev B.H.**

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Resume. The quality of life of patients and the period of adaptation to prostheses are studied as the main indicators in the assessment of clinical effectiveness. Modern studies show that digitally prepared prostheses are psychologically and functionally accepted by the patient faster, and the number of visits to the doctor for correction is significantly reduced.

Keywords: defect, caries, hard palate, atrophy, cleft lip, prosthesis.

ТЎЛИҚ ТИШСИЗ БЕМОРЛАРНИНГ КЛИНИК ҲОЛАТИДАН КЕЛИБ ЧИҚИБ, АНЪАНАВИЙ ЁКИ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯНИ ТАНЛАШ МЕЗОНЛАРИНИ ВА ДАВОЛАШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ**Олимов С.Ш., Рабиев Б.Ҳ.**

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Резюме. Клиник самарадорликни баҳолашда беморларнинг ҳаёт сифати ва протезларга мослашиш (адаптация) даври асосий кўрсаткич сифатида ўрганилмоқда. Замонавий тадқиқотлар шуни кўрсатадики, рақамли усулда тайёрланган протезлар бемор томонидан психологик ва функционал жиҳатдан тезроқ қабул қилинади ва коррекция учун шифокорга мурожаатлар сони сезиларли даражада камаяди.

Калит сўзлар: нуқсон, кариес, қаттиқ танглай, атрофия, лаб юганчаси, протез.

УЛУЧШЕНИЕ КРИТЕРИЕВ ВЫБОРА ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ИЛИ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ С УЧЕТОМ КЛИНИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ПОЛНОЙ АДЕНТИЕЙ**Олимов С.Ш., Рабиев Б.Х.**

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Резюме. В качестве основных показателей оценки клинической эффективности изучаются качество жизни пациентов и период адаптации к протезам. Современные исследования показывают, что изготовленные с помощью цифровых технологий протезы быстрее воспринимаются пациентом психологически и функционально, а количество визитов к врачу для коррекции значительно сокращается.

Ключевые слова: дефект, кариес, твёрдый неба, атрофия, уздечки верхней губы, протез.

Relevance. In recent years, the problem of complete edentulism (adentia) has become one of the most urgent issues of not only dental, but also socio-economic importance. The relevance of this topic can be justified by several important factors. Demographic changes and increased needs are increasing the average life expectancy of the population all over the world, including in Uzbekistan. This leads to an increase in the number of elderly patients with complete edentulism. According to statistical data, a significant part of the population over 60 years of age needs complete removable dentures. The disadvantages of traditional methods create a number of difficulties in the process of making dentures using traditional methods (using plaster models, wax bases). The subsidence of the denture can change its volume during the polymerization of the plastic, which leads to an inaccurate fit of the denture to the jaw. Even small mistakes made in the laboratory stages worsen the fixation and retention of the prosthesis. The period of adaptation to the prosthesis, getting used to traditional prostheses can be long and painful for the patient [1,3,5].

Today, a set of targeted practical measures aimed at modernizing the healthcare system and gradually adapting it to international standards is being consistently implemented in our country. As part of the ongoing reforms, special attention is paid to the development and implementation of modern and highly effective approaches to the prevention, early detection and complex treatment of pathological conditions of the oral mucosa. In this regard, the following tasks have been set: increasing the efficiency, quality and accessibility of medical care, as well as forming a medical standardization system, introducing high-tech

methods of diagnosis and treatment [2,6,9]. These tasks form one of the priority and socially significant scientific directions aimed at introducing into clinical practice improved approaches to the effectiveness of prostheses made by modern and traditional methods in completely edentulous patients.

The purpose of the study was to compare the clinical and functional effectiveness of removable prostheses prepared using traditional and modern (digital) technologies in the orthopedic treatment of edentulous patients and to improve the quality of life of elderly patients.

Materials and methods. This scientific study was focused on evaluating the clinical effectiveness of fully removable prostheses made by modern technologies in the case of complete edentulousness. In the research, the compatibility, fixation and accuracy level of the base of prostheses prepared using traditional methods and modern digital technologies were compared. The study was based on the complex application of clinical, laboratory and digital analysis methods. This made it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of prostheses made using different technologies on a scientific basis. The research was carried out in several stages. In the first stage, selection of patients and clinical examination were carried out. In the second stage, diagnostic models were prepared and prostheses were developed using various technologies. In the third stage, the accuracy of the prosthesis base, its compatibility with the mucous membrane of the jaw, and its fixation were evaluated. The results obtained in the fourth stage were statistically analyzed.

From an anatomical perspective, the most favorable arch shapes are the semi-oval and truncated-conical, which have a positive effect on retention and stability. Their incidence among patients reaches 55%. Furthermore, increased atrophy of the denture base tissues often occurs under the denture base. Wearing removable dentures disrupts microcirculation under the denture base, which subsequently leads to the development and progression of atrophy in the denture base tissues [4].

Based on the above, it can be concluded that prolonged use of complete dentures causes a response from the denture base tissues. In most cases, this is expressed as increased atrophic processes occurring in the denture base tissues, and, in particular, a decrease in the thickness and compliance of the mucous membrane. The severity of these responses depends on the patient's age, the design, and the chemical composition of the dentures. The primary goal of prosthetic treatment for edentulous patients is to address essential functional and aesthetic needs while improving quality of life. Complete plate dentures must provide retention and stability in edentulous jaws, while artificial teeth must integrate and interact with the tissues and organs of the maxillofacial region, as well as optimally participate in chewing, speech production, and breathing [2].

Results and discussions. A pathological oval defect exposing a portion of the dental root below the cemento-enamel junction in the upper edge of the maxillary dental arch is 9.8 ± 0.6 mm thick in the area of the molars in the complete edentulous group, while in the area of the premolars and anterior teeth it does not exceed 7 mm. A certain pattern exists, which is associated with the fact that the longer the time since tooth extraction, the more pronounced the reduction in bone volume in the dental arches of edentulous jaws. Moreover, the atrophic process can be aggravated by prosthetic treatments, which are performed without taking into account the individual anatomical and topographic features of the tissue structure of the denture bed. Currently, the main treatments for complete edentulousness are complete removable plate dentures and prosthetic restorations. Plate dentures are the most popular, while dental implantation remains an alternative method of choice for patients, as it has a certain range of medical contraindications. The choice of traditional removable dentures is associated with ease of manufacture, low cost, and accessibility for all segments of the population [4]. A wide range of etiological factors for complete tooth loss, as well as pathogenetic mechanisms of their formation, with numerous remote structures, are considered. At the same time, the triangular-pointed shape of the dental arch ridge causes a number of difficulties during prosthetics, contributing to the development of traumatic erosions on the oral mucosa and reducing the stability of a complete removable plate denture [3,8]. Bone protrusions of the dental arch in the area of the denture bed pose certain difficulties in prosthetics. In general, complete dentures on the upper jaw are in more favorable functional conditions than on the lower jaw. Bone atrophy of the dental arch is uneven in the upper and lower jaws: the upper jaw atrophies more slowly than the lower jaw, and atrophy of the upper jaw is centripetal (that is, from the outside in), while that of the lower jaw is centrifugal. The human upper jaw has a number of anatomical features: in the area of the median sagittal suture, the mucous membrane thins and prevents the denture from settling into the tissue of the denture bed, which is explained by the absence of a submucosal layer and tight fusion with the periosteum [2].

Meanwhile, issues related to improving the retention, safety, and functionality of complete removable dentures on edentulous jaws, taking into account the individual anatomical and topographic variability of the maxillofacial region, remain unresolved. It is important to note that a number of domestic and international researchers are seriously studying these issues [2]. Currently, various methods have been developed and applied in clinical dentistry to improve retention and stabilize complete removable plate dentures on jaws

with varying degrees of dental arch atrophy. For this purpose, surgical techniques and adhesives are used in practice, taking into account individual anatomical and topographic features as much as possible [4].

However, difficulties exist in the medical and social rehabilitation of patients with complete tooth loss. After receiving complete dentures, only 23.7% of patients actively use them, using them for eating (11.4%) or communicating (7.0%). Meanwhile, more than half of patients develop various pathologies of the oral mucosa under the bases of complete dentures. According to several authors, such patients who seek orthopedic care at municipal dental institutions for the purpose of re-prosthetics constitute approximately 40% [2].

3D printing technology is based on the principle of additive manufacturing. These technologies create new opportunities in orthopedic dentistry. Based on the results of clinical and laboratory studies, the following conclusions were drawn [4,8]. There are significant differences between traditional and digital technologies in the manufacture of complete removable prostheses in patients with complete edentia. Digital technologies, in particular CAD/CAM technology in dentistry, have shown high efficiency in improving the accuracy of the prosthesis base and its compliance with the maxillary mucosa [3,6].

When analyzing the compliance of the prosthesis base with the maxillary mucosa using the 3D surface scanning method, it was found that the average deviation in prostheses manufactured using CAD/CAM technology is 2–3 times lower than in the traditional method. The fixation of complete removable prostheses directly depends on the accuracy of the prosthesis base and its compliance with the maxillary mucosa. The fixation mechanism is based on physical principles such as Adhesion and Cohesion [2,5].

Conclusion. When evaluating prosthesis fixation using the Dynamometry method, it was found that the fixation force of prostheses manufactured using CAD/CAM technology is on average 30–40% higher than that of the traditional method. Although 3D printing technology, i.e. 3D printing in dentistry, has higher accuracy than the traditional method, in some cases the printed layers can cause microdeviations on the surface of the prosthesis base [1]. When assessing patient satisfaction using the Patient satisfaction questionnaire method, it was observed that the functional convenience, aesthetics and overall satisfaction level of prostheses manufactured using CAD/CAM technology are high. Modern digital technologies allow optimizing the manufacturing process of fully removable prostheses in orthopedic dentistry and improving clinical results[2].

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